

DIGITALIZATION AND PHYSICAL INACTIVITY: CHALLENGES FOR THE PHYSICAL HEALTH OF THE YOUNGER GENERATION

N.D. Oryngaliyeva¹, A.A. Dosmurzayeva²

Lecturer at the Department of Anatomy, Clinical Anatomy, and Histology¹

First-year student of the Faculty of Pediatrics²

Karakalpakstan Medical Institute, Nukus, Uzbekistan^{1,2}

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Abstract. *In recent decades, digitalization has permeated all areas of life, including education, leisure, and communication. One of the negative consequences of this process is a decrease in physical activity among children and adolescents — hypodynamia. This article reviews modern studies reflecting the impact of digital technologies on the level of physical activity and overall physical health of children. It highlights the main risks associated with physical inactivity, such as obesity, postural disorders, reduced endurance, and increased fatigue. Possible preventive and corrective measures are presented, including the role of the family, school, and the state.*

Keywords: *digitalization, children, adolescents, physical inactivity, physical health, motor activity, screens, lifestyle.*

Relevance. Today's children grow up with unprecedented access to digital devices. Smartphones, tablets, computers, and interactive whiteboards have become an integral part of their daily lives. However, behind the convenience and access to information lie hidden threats: reduced time for active play, walks, and sports.

Methodology. Physical inactivity—a decrease in physical activity—is becoming a widespread phenomenon among children and adolescents. According to the WHO, about 80% of teenagers worldwide do not meet the recommended levels of physical activity. Low levels of physical activity in childhood lead to the development of chronic diseases later in life, reduced productivity, deterioration in psycho-emotional states, and difficulties with social adaptation. Therefore, studying the connection between digitalization and physical development has become increasingly important for preserving the health of the younger generation [1,6]. The main issue is that uncontrolled use of digital technologies, especially in preschool and early school age, can negatively affect the natural mechanisms of psychomotor development and lower the overall level of physical activity [5,19].

It is becoming evident that further research is needed to develop diagnostic methods to reliably assess a child's sensitivity to screen exposure and its long-term consequences. Future studies should identify the key mechanisms and causal links between digital technology use and brain health [4,15].

The relevance of this topic is due to the need for a balanced approach to digitalizing the children's environment, especially in the context of growing dependence on digital devices. Studies show that excessive gadget use may delay psychomotor development and reduce children's overall physical activity. This requires scientific analysis and the development of recommendations for the optimal use of digital technologies in childhood.

The aim of this study is to review and analyze existing research materials on the impact of computers, gadgets, and other information and communication technologies on children's physical activity levels and to examine the risks of physical inactivity as a consequence of digitalization.

A review of the literature shows that digitalization is directly related to the rise in physical inactivity. Most studies demonstrate that children who spend more than 3 hours a day in front of screens show lower physical development indicators and face more frequent health problems. At the same time, integrating digital technologies into physical education (e.g., interactive simulators, fitness apps) can become part of the solution [7,13].

Computer use in the educational process is a significant factor in causing fatigue in both boys and girls, although the response varies by gender. Researchers found [4,17] that using computers in class leads to diverse changes in the studied indicators. Children who spend more than 4 hours a day in front of screens engage less in physical games and sports, leading to physical inactivity, weight gain, and posture issues. Among children who use gadgets for more than 3–4 hours per day, decreased coordination, worsened fine motor skills (e.g., grasping, writing, drawing), and slower reaction speeds were observed. Moderate digital technology use (up to 2 hours per day) can contribute to the development of spatial thinking, memory, and processing speed. However, excessive screen time reduces attention span and weakens interpersonal communication skills. Interactive learning platforms and active video games have a less negative impact on psychomotor skills than passive content consumption (e.g., watching videos or scrolling social media) [8,11].

The rapid development and integration of information technologies into education using electronic learning tools have already led to a deterioration in children's health. Gadgets, having become an inseparable part of life, influence not only consciousness and cognition but also physiological processes. Despite their potential developmental benefits, researchers warn of significant risks, especially for children under five and those exposed to screens for more than two hours daily [3,12].

Scientists advise against the routine integration of digital technologies into children's everyday lives, as healthy development requires creative activities, role-playing games, and real-world sensory experiences. According to research [9,10,16], children engrossed in computer games like quests and arcades demonstrate lower imagination scores compared to their peers without such habits.

Excessive gadget use contributes to several problems: vision deterioration, reduced academic performance, mental health disorders, musculoskeletal system diseases, and more. Documented effects also include changes in sleep cycles, memory mechanisms, attention, physical development indicators, and posture. Studies show that high levels of digitalization reduce mental performance, slow cognitive development, and increase anxiety and hyperactivity in children [6,14,18].

A particularly concerning risk of digital overuse is computer and internet addiction, characterized by a lack of interest in the real world and a preference for virtual environments [2,10].

Results and discussion. Research findings [17] show that about 13% of children aged 7–10 exhibit signs of internet addiction, and with the increasing trend toward early digital exposure, the risk of growing dependency is evident.

The number of children developing computer and internet addiction continues to rise, creating challenges for their full psychological and psychosocial development.

Conclusion. The use of digital devices for education, entertainment, and development must be guided by strict hygienic standards and monitoring. Children encounter information technology from the earliest months of life, and its influence only increases with age. However, the lack of large-scale national studies makes it difficult to fully assess the long-term effects of digitalization on children's health and development [8].

Digitalization brings both opportunities and risks to children's physical health. Physical inactivity is becoming a major challenge for the future generation. Systemic action is required at the family, school, and government levels to promote a culture of active living, combine digital resources with physical activity, and strengthen preventive efforts. Only a comprehensive approach can preserve and improve children's health in today's rapidly evolving digital world.

Thus, a scientifically grounded analysis of digitalization's consequences is needed to determine when technologies can foster development and when they pose risks to children's physical well-being.

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